

Supporting the Hypothesis Creation Process via Patterns Illumination in Knowledge Graphs

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Extended Abstract

Recent years have witnessed the gradual adoption of *knowledge graphs* into the data-management workflows of galleries, libraries, archival institutions, and museums around the world [1, 3, 7]. Otherwise known as *linked data*, knowledge graphs represent data via relationships between objects, and between objects and property values. This makes them particularly suited for modelling complex relational data. A shared collection of common schemas and vocabularies on top of this also ensures that these data are, for the most part, self explanatory and unambiguous, and that any dataset that is modelled as knowledge graph can fairly easily be linked with any other knowledge graph, thereby effectively creating one large dataset. As linking knowledge graphs becomes more commonplace within the humanities, new patterns emerge which span what used to be separate datasets. This offers great opportunities for scholars and researchers, who can now potentially ask and answer many new research questions.

Research questions are traditionally derived from scholarly literature, but can, in more recent times, also be inferred directly from one's data. Without extensive study, however, it is often not known a priori what questions these data might hold the answers to: even if accompanied by rich metadata, these alone often provide insufficient information to support scholars during this process, potentially limiting them to the confines of scholarly literature or to sparks of their own imagination. Many potentially interesting and novel insights may remain undiscovered as a result. This work aims to support scholars during this early stage of the scientific workflow, by highlighting potentially interesting patterns in knowledge graphs that may form the building blocks for new research questions, and which can be used as evidence for already existing lines of research.

Pattern discovery on graph-shaped data can take on various forms. In this work, we specifically look for *generalised graph patterns*, which are frequently occurring substructures in knowledge graphs that are statistically significant and which tell us something about groups of individuals (or *things*) [4]. For this purpose, these patterns, which themselves are represented as graphs, allow for one

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or more of their vertices to be replaced by special variables which matches any value from a certain probability distribution, rather than just the single value of the original vertex. What distribution is used depends on the type and range of possible values for that vertex, and can include Normal distributions for numerical and temporal properties (e.g. *age* and *duration*) and uniform distributions for classes or datatypes (e.g. *all women* and *all integers*) as well as for collections of words (e.g. from a controlled vocabulary).

To highlight *generalised graph patterns* in knowledge graphs, we introduce a bottom-up approach to discover such patterns directly from the data themselves, by leveraging both statistics and semantics to guide the discovery process. Concretely, our method employs a two-step approach, by first enumerating the most basic patterns (given some user-defined criteria) and by then extending these to form ever more complex patterns. By allowing the patterns to grow more precise with each following iteration our method obtains the so-called *anytime* property, which means that scholars can terminate the process at their leisure and still obtain potentially interesting, albeit more coarse-grain, results, whereas, if left running for longer, more fine-grained patterns are found.

To accommodate the exploration and analysis of the discovered patterns our method includes a simple facet browser, build upon open standards, that runs in any arbitrary web browser, and which facilitates the filtering of patterns over various dimensions. The filtered selection can be saved in a separate file (together with updated provenance information and other metadata) which itself can be opened in the facet browser for further analysis or shared with fellow scholars, thereby facilitating reuse and reproducibility. Finally, to lessen the semantic gap, the patterns can be viewed as SPARQL⁵queries (with which most scholars in our target group are familiar with) and optionally visualised as an interactive graph.

A focused user study was conducted to evaluate the patterns and the method that discovered them. To increase the value of the responses, it was decided to personally invite various prominent experts from the humanities to participate in this study. A total of 13 of said experts agreed to participate, corresponding to a fair response rate of 31%. After a general introduction, each participant was asked to assess several hand-picked patterns on various dimensions of *interestingness* [2], including *novelty*, *utility*, and *validity*, as well as on *interpretability*. In addition, the participants were asked about their familiarity with the topics associated with this research, and about their perceived usefulness of the method and the patterns it yields. All responses were recorded on a Likert scale and on free-form text.

The dataset used in our experiments contained the civil records from 5.5 million Dutch citizen who were alive between 1811 and 1974. Each record includes information about a person’s pedigree, marital status, occupation, and location, as well as various important life events including birth, death, and becoming a parent. All patterns presented during the user study were discovered⁶in this

⁵ The SPARQL specification is available at www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-query

<pre> SELECT ?\$v_i\$?\$v_j\$ WHERE { ?\$v_i\$ has_gender Male . ?\$v_i\$ has_occupation H.61220 . ?\$v_i\$ has_age ?\$v_k\$. ?\$v_j\$ has_subject ?\$v_i\$. ?\$v_j\$ has_type Marriage . FILTER (?\$v_k\$ == "29"^^int) } </pre>	<pre> SELECT ?\$v_i\$ WHERE { ?\$v_i\$ has_gender Female . ?\$v_i\$ has_firstName ?\$v_j\$. ?\$v_i\$ has_familyName ?\$v_k\$. FILTER (REGEX(?\$v_j\$, "[a-z]{2,14}\s[a-z]{2,14}") && REGEX(?\$v_k\$, "[a-z]{3,16}")) } </pre>
<p>"In this population sample, 1,238 out of 100,000 records are about 29 year old married men who work in agriculture."</p>	<p>"In this population sample, 13,632 out of 100,000 records are about women with two first names between 2 and 14 characters each, and with a family name between 3 and 16 characters."</p>

Listing 1: Two graph patterns that were found during our experiments, encoded as SPARQL queries, together with their natural language description. Note that, for brevity, the namespaces have been omitted.

dataset, including the two examples that are listed in Listing 1. As can be inferred from the natural language description, the left-hand pattern covers the set of all 29 year old men who are married and who work in the agricultural sector, which accounts for 1,238 individuals in the dataset. The graph pattern on the right accounts for 13,632 people, and encompasses all women with two first names between two and 14 characters each, and with a family name between three and 16 characters.

An analysis of the responses from our user study (Fig. 1) suggested that, in general, the participants were rather critical about the patterns they were presented with. The number of people who were very negative differed considerably, however, as is also evident from the low agreement amongst participants (Kendall’s $W = 0.14$ [6]). Most critical (64%) were these participants about *validity*, which is interesting since the patterns are generalisations of the original data, rather than predictions, and are therefore as valid as the data they were discovered in. That the patterns were nevertheless perceived as invalid by many of the participants suggests that there was a mismatch between the experts’ expectations and the output of our method.

To better understand the critical responses we conducted a factor analysis of the tested dimensions. This analysis showed a clear separation between the factor loading of *utility* ($0.90\lambda_1$) and *validity* ($0.88\lambda_1$) on one hand, and *interpretability* ($0.97\lambda_2$) on the other. This suggests that both *utility* and *validity* contributed to the same latent component, which we can perhaps interpret as a measure of *effectiveness*, whereas *interpretability* measured an entirely different component of its own. More peculiar, however, were the factor loadings belonging to *novelty*, which enjoyed significant cross loadings on both components ($-0.54\lambda_1 + 0.40\lambda_2$), suggesting that this dimension is a combination of high interpretability and low effectiveness. This creates an interesting paradox, in which participants rate the

⁶ An implementation of our method that was used during the experiments is available at github.com/wxwilcke/hypodisc

Fig. 1. Responses on a 5-point Likert scale (Kendall’s $W = 0.14$) about the perceived novelty, validity, utility, and interpretability of the presented graph patterns.

effectiveness based on the method’s ability to discover known and useful patterns, but value novel insights for their perceived validity and utility as long as they are easy to understand.

When taking the responses on familiarity into account, it can be observed that, overall, the participants were unfamiliar to moderately familiar with the core concepts. This suggests the existence of a significant semantic gap between the technical background of the participants and the skills required to fully comprehend the method and the patterns it yields. Moreover, correlation tests indicate that there is a strong positive correlation ($0.51 \leq \text{Kendall’s } \tau \leq 0.77$ [5]) between being critical about the patterns and having a limited technical background. Several participants also mentioned that this skill difference made them uncertain when assessing the patterns, which is corroborated by the low self-reported confidence (Kendall’s $W = 0.85$ [6]).

To conclude, the aim of this work was to support scholars and researchers during the early steps of their scientific workflows, by discovering and highlighting novel and potentially interesting patterns in knowledge graphs in the humanities, which can be used to form new research hypotheses or to support existing ones. An evaluation of our method, while rather critical at first glance, revealed several interesting insights about both our method and about its potential users, opening the door for future research along these lines. Most particularly, from our findings, it can be argued that discovering *novel* patterns should perhaps not be the primary goal of future methods, but rather the discovery of explainable connections between known and grounded patterns.

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